

MANUFACTURING OF PRIMARY AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES WITH VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN INFUSION (VARI)

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SUMMARY

The liquid resin infusion (LRI) process has proved its high potential for enhancing production efficiency, especially in terms of reducing manufacturing cost of CFRP parts for aerospace applications. Therefore, the Institute of Structures and Design of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Stuttgart developed the Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion process (VARI). Various test parts and 9 m long CFRP C-spars demonstrated impressively the potential of VARI for a cost effective, reliable, robust, and reproducible high quality manufacturing process. However, commercial production required further development steps in handling techniques of non-crimp fabric and automated process control. The solutions will be outlined in the paper, as well as new developments in process monitoring with advanced capabilities for quality control are described. Due to these results a closed related LRI process, the Modified Vacuum Infusion process (MVI), was developed in collaboration between Airbus Deutschland GmbH and the German Aerospace Center in Stuttgart. Airbus Deutschland will produce C-spars and ribs of the Airbus A 380 vertical tail plane using the MVI process. A brief description of the introduction in the production line will finish the paper.

KEYWORDS: Liquid resin infusion, LRI, Liquid composite moulding, LCM, Vacuum Resin Infusion, industrial production, aircraft structure, process monitoring, processing

INTRODUCTION

The LRI process **V**acuum **A**ssisted **R**esin **I**nfusion (VARI) was developed at the Institute of Structures and Design at the German Aerospace Center in Stuttgart to provide an cost

efficient alternative to the mainly used manufacturing processes such as prepreg or RTM processes [1, 2]. Various test parts demonstrated impressively the potential of the VARI process for a cost effective, reliable, robust, and reproducible high quality manufacturing process. In close collaboration with Airbus Deutschland GmbH in Bremen and Stade, the German Aerospace Center in Stuttgart has manufactured several 9 m long C-spars to prove the industrial readiness and additionally the enhancing production efficiency of the VARI process. However, commercial mass production has required further development in lay up of non-crimp fabric in the mould, process control and quality management. Therefore, Airbus Deutschland GmbH and the Institute of Structures and Design of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) further improved the VARI process resulting in the **Modified Vacuum Infusion** process (MVI), which will be certified for the production of primary aircraft structures [3]. Airbus Deutschland GmbH will manufacture spars and ribs of the new Airbus A 380 vertical tail plane using this improved vacuum assisted infusion process (MVI). To meet the necessary mechanical properties, as well as the production efficiency, non-crimp fabric (Saertex) and high temperature curing resin (RTM6 Hexcel) will be used for the production of these primary structure parts of the A 380 vertical tail plane. Among others, the simple lay-up by an adapted mould design and the automated process control unit assure the enhancing production efficiency.

VARI-PROCESS

The goal in development of the VARI-process was to provide a low cost process which enables the industry to manufacture high performance composite aircraft structures having fibre volume fractions up to 60 %. Therefore, low tooling and labour cost had to be achieved. Additionally, expensive process equipment like autoclaves or heated press should be avoided, which leads to a vacuum assisted process. The usage of dry fabrics and liquid resins in an infusion process also reduces the material cost compared to prepreg materials. The mentioned demand on a vacuum assisted resin infusion process could be met for various resin systems and fabrics using the VARI-process. For understanding the goal of the process development a closer look at the resin flow behaviour in a 1-dimensional direction is appropriate. The resin flow through dry fabric could be described by Darcy's law, for a Newton fluid streaming through a porous medium [4]. Whereas the resin front velocity is

$$v = \frac{K \cdot \Delta p}{\eta(1-\varphi) \cdot s} \quad (1)$$

depending on the permeability of the dry fabric (K), the differential pressure between resin inlet and front (Δp), the dynamic resin viscosity (η), the fibre volume fraction (φ) and the distance between resin inlet and front (s). The integration by $v = ds/dt$ leads to

$$\int_0^{x_f} s ds = \int_0^{t_f} \frac{K \cdot \Delta p}{\eta(1-\varphi)} dt \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} x_f^2 = \frac{K \cdot \Delta p}{\eta(1-\varphi)} t_f \quad (2)$$

It could be easily seen, that the maximum achievable distance has a square dependence to the infusion time. By given permeability of the fabric, pot life time and viscosity of the resin and the maximum atmospherically pressure difference of 1000 hPa, the achievable distance is not sufficient for infusion of large parts. Normally, large aircraft parts are shells with a very small thickness area relation. Therefore, the preferred resin flow direction for a vacuum assisted process is the thickness direction of the fabric, what is one of the basic principals of the VARI-process. The impregnation of the fabric in thickness direction is realized by a particular resin distribution fabric distributing the resin over the lay-up surface. The principal of the distribution fabric is known since the 1970's, nevertheless, the best known usage is at the Seeman Composite Resin Infusion Moulding (SCRIMP) process [5]. Another very important principal is the manipulation of the process parameters, pressure and temperature. The fibre volume fraction as well as the porosity of the structural parts is controlled by the variation of pressure and temperature, i.e. the resin viscosity. Furthermore, excellent part quality could only be achieved in correct adjustment of the mentioned parameters and knowledge of the resin front

Figure 1: Schematic lay-up

movement in the lay-up. Figure 1 shows the principal lay-up for the VARI-process. The lay-up is almost similar to a conventional vacuum bagging except the resin distributing fabric. Between the carbon and the distribution fabric a release film has to be placed to allow the separation of these layers after curing. The most important item is to ensure the proper impermeability of the lay-up to prevent voids in the part caused by any set up leakage. After evacuating the set up the resin will be distributed over the lay-up surface in order to impregnate the carbon fibres in the thickness direction, which is demonstrated in a section drawing, Fig. 1, by the wedge shaped resin front. The set up of a flat test plate with a resin infusion line on a heated table is shown in Fig. 2, where also

Figure 2: Laboratory set up during infusion

the resin front in the distribution fabric is visible. The infusion process is finished by resin pouring into the resin-trap at the vents and followed by the curing process.

TEST PARTS

In order to approve the process cost efficiency and the part quality, various test parts with Saertex non-crimp fabric and Hexcel RTM6 resin have been manufactured in collaboration between Airbus Deutschland GmbH and DLR Stuttgart. In the beginning several C-spars have been cured in a 2.3 m long nickel steel mould followed by real sized 9 m long spars to examine whether the up-scaled parts could be produced as efficiently and reliably as the laboratory tests showed earlier. Due to the growing size of the parts some changes in the process set up had to be made. Especially the discrete located vents and resin inlets (Fig. 3) required an increasing set up time, which could not have been accepted in case of mass production. Furthermore, sources of errors for potential leakage at an imprecise lay-up could affect the product quality. Therefore, vents and resin inlets have been designed as lines, preferably made of an especially shaped silicon tube to avoid pressure increasing zones at the edge of the tubes. As expected from former experience based on some small test samples, problems appeared with respect to the shape and the

fibre volume fraction in the corner area, whereas the laminate quality of the C-spar's bottom and webs was excellent. Fibre volume fractions at an average of 59 % and porosity fractions lower than 1 % have been achieved.

The test parts demonstrated the reliability, cost efficiency and reproducibility of the VARI-process. However, the corner shape had to be improved in order that the process be implemented into the Airbus production line.

Figure 3: 2 m test spar

IMPROVEMENTS

One fundamental problem in manufacturing C-spars using vacuum assisted processes is to ensure a proper shape of the corner area. Friction forces occur between the carbon layers at the bottom and webs of the C-spar. This prevents the fabric of slipping completely into the corner; hence the lay-up stretches over the mould corner. To achieve a proper corner shape, i.e., to avoid stretching of the lay-up, several types of thrust pieces have been investigated. A considerable improvement was attained by an approach with additional mechanical forces into the corner area. Different fixture concepts were designed for an appropriate test mould and several C-spars have been manufactured with the aim to ensure the capability for up scaling to real sized 9 m long C-spars and 3 m long ribs with curved webs. The successful concept is shown in Figure 4. Two rigs fixed at the mould apply a mechanical

Figure 4: Concept of mechanical fixture

force onto the fixture, which will be transferred to the metallic angle plates, located on top of the lay-up. The fixture is made of steel with a coefficient of thermal expansion corresponding to that of the mould. This ensures a constant cavity between the angel plates and the mould. The resulting C-spars built with the fixture in the test moulds exceeded the demanded quality in the corner - that is to say fibre volume fractions above 54 % and porosity fractions smaller than 1.5 %.

Furthermore, investigations on a special mould design were carried out. The aim was to develop moulds with integrated vent lines to reduce the set up time and hence the labour cost, which has a relevant share of the total part cost. Integrated vents and inlets have been known for years in the RTM process, where holes are drilled through the mould and the resin tubes connected at the assembled fittings. Figure 5 shows details of the design approach for the

Figure 5: Detail of vent line in the mould web

mould web. The vent duct was milled into the mould's web surface, located beneath the carbon fabric. A step was built in for fixing a perforated metal plate that prevents the carbon fibre of blocking the duct while being evacuated. The connection to the resin tubes is realized with the duct ending at the end of the mould and a short tube wrapped by tacky tape was put into the duct. This design allows using only common resin tubes without any fittings etc. Thus, cleaning of the duct after curing by ripping off the perforated metal plate together with the resin in the duct is easy to establish.

HANDLING OF NON-CRIMP FABRIC

The handling of the non-crimp fabric was identified as having a cost reduction potential. Besides manufacturing cost, a simple and careful handling technique improves the parts quality by ensuring correct fibre angles and warping free lay-up. Investigations on two concepts have been carried out. At the DLR Institute of Structural Mechanics in Braunschweig a vacuum preform support [6] has been developed, having the inverted shape of the inner mould face reduced by an offset for the preform thickness. The non-

crimp fabric is placed over the vacuum preform support. Fixation is achieved by an airflow generating a vacuum. Thereafter the support is positioned within the mould. After removing the support, the fabric will remain in the mould. The preferred approach at the Institute of Structures and Design in Stuttgart is a handling system with a fabric slide guide moving over the mould, where the non-crimp fabric will be positioned directly from the carrying roller. To avoid any wrapping during positioning of the fabric on the previous layer, there is no relative speed between the fabric sliding off the handling system and the mould itself. Figure 6 illustrates a test set up for the fabric slide guide

Figure 6: Fabric slide guide

guide handling system. The advantages of this system are that the non-crimp fabric will be handled only once and the system could be enhanced by cutting and lay-up automation equipment, as well as a quality control system.

PROCESS CONTROL

In a laboratory production, only vacuum pump, vacuum measurement devices and resin traps are needed for the infusion process. The resin traps must be gas impervious and heated, in case if a hot curing resin is used. Heating the mould can either be realized by a heated table, i.e. a heated mould, or an furnace with temperature control. Due to the size of the Airbus A 380 parts, there is presently no furnace available for these dimensions at the Airbus plant in Stade. Therefore, autoclaves will be used for curing for the time being. Pressure adjustments at the vents and inlet will be operated by hand with valves and clamps in the laboratory process. Also the filling level of the inlet resin trap is visually observed and refilled if necessary. However, manual process control can not be accepted in the production line of Airbus Deutschland GmbH. Therefore an integrated process management system, allowing an independent process control without any manual input has to be provided. The scheme of the process pressure control at the management system

Figure 7: Scheme of process pressure control

for one C-spar is illustrated in Figure 7. Furthermore, high demands on the process management system are made to allow the parallel manufacturing of several parts in one autoclave slot. To fulfil the requirements a process management and control system will be provided at Airbus Deutschland GmbH for parallel infusion of 2 C-spars and 4 rib with in total 120 kg of Hexcel RTM6 resin.

NEW PROCESS MONITORING TECHNIQUE

As mentioned further, knowledge of resin front movements in the lay-up is essential for the design of infusion process at geometrically complex parts. Therefore, new investigations in process and flow front monitoring are being conducted at the Institute of Structures and Design at the German Aerospace Center. Visual observation of the infusion process is applicable to obtain more experience about resin flows in the distribution fabric. However, resin flows in the whole lay-up should be known to prevent insufficient resin infusion, trapped air in the fabric or other defects. Dielectric and fibre optic sensors demonstrated their potential in the flow front monitoring [7, 8], nevertheless, these sensors must be embedded in the lay-up or the mould. Yet, new possibilities in flow front and process monitoring are given by the visual accessibility of the VARI process lay-up whilst processing. The new, innovative approach is to use the lock-in thermography for flow front and process monitoring. Lock-in thermography is a technique provided for remote non destructive testing of structural components to detect non visible cracks and delaminations beneath the parts surface [9, 10]. The principal of lock-in thermography, i.e. to monitor the thermal response of an illuminated surface,

shows the capability to measure the flow front velocity and shape during the ongoing process. First results of investigations by observing the infusion process of a flat plate can be seen in figure 8, where the flow front in constant time steps is visible.

Figure 8: Flow front monitoring by thermography

Moreover, void air by improper sealing of the vacuum bagging could be detected; hence, the thermal diffusivity of the lay-up will change the parts thermal response. Further investigations on several test parts need to be carried out in order to calibrate the thermal response with the defined faults implemented in the test parts. Nevertheless, the first results of process and flow front monitoring encourage the further development of a process monitoring system to enable quality control while processing.

CONCLUSION

The vacuum assisted resin infusion process (VARI) has proved its reliability, cost efficiency and reproducibility potential for manufacturing high performance aircraft structures by manufacturing several test parts. Hence, C-spars and ribs of the Airbus A 380 vertical tail plane will be produced using the improved VARI process, the MVI process, at Airbus Deutschland GmbH in Stade. The tasks for industrialisation of the process have been outlined in this paper. Investigations of serial mould design, fabric handling techniques and corner shape optimisation have been carried out and solutions have been successfully developed. A coherent manufacturing environment was developed by adapting the process set up to the industrial setting. A significant cost reduction in addition to reproducibility and high quality criteria have been achieved in this industrial production process.

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